

Implementing Song in Teaching Listening Comprehension at Muhammadiyah University of Jakarta

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ABSTRACTS - The paper attempts to investigate the use of song in teaching listening comprehension for students' English department at Muhammadiyah University of Jakarta. The researcher used descriptive qualitative method. The subject of the study was students at sixth semester of Muhammadiyah University of Jakarta. The instrument and the procedure of data collection were used observation and questionnaire. The activities of the implementation involved the use of song in teaching listening. The paper answers the following questions: 1. What are the impacts of using song-learning English? 2. How frequently listening song to improve the listening skills for student? 3. What are the common difficulties that face the respondents in the questionnaire implemented in this paper in terms of listening comprehension? Thus, the paper aims to find the factors influencing English listening comprehension and the strategies to be taken that might improve students' listening comprehension. The paper indicates that the current problems face students in developing listening comprehension skills are speed speech, limited knowledge of vocabulary, and limited knowledge of the song lyric. Further studies could be conducted to gauge the issue of listening comprehension using other kind of multi media such TV or Movies in improving students listening skills.

Keywords: Song, Listening Comprehension, and University

ABSTRAK - Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menganalisis penggunaan lagu dalam pembelajaran Listening Comprehension di Universitas Muhammadiyah Jakarta. Peneliti menggunakan metode deskriptif kualitatif dengan subjek penelitian mahasiswa semester 6 di universitas Muhammadiyah Jakarta. Dengan prosedur dan instrumen pengumpulan data menggunakan observasi dan kuisioner. Adapun permasalahan yang akan dijawab dalam penelitian ini adalah: 1. Apa pengaruh penggunaan lagu dalam mempelajari bahasa Inggris? 2. Seberapa sering mendengarkan lagu dapat meningkatkan kemampuan Listening comprehension mahasiswa? 3. Apa saja kesulitan-kesulitan umum yang dihadapi oleh responden yang mengisi kuisioner terkait dengan Listening Comprehension? Penelitian ini berupaya untuk mengetahui faktor yang mempengaruhi kemampuan Listening Comprehension mahasiswa dan strategi yang dapat digunakan untuk meningkatkan kemampuan mereka. Hasil temuan menunjukkan permasalahan yang dihadapi oleh mahasiswa dalam mengembangkan kemampuan Listening Comprehension terbagi menjadi 3 bagian yaitu kecepatan ujaran, minimnya penguasaan kosakata dan minimnya pengetahuan mengenai lirik lagu. Untuk penelitian lainnya dapat mengembangkan kajian yang membahas terkait penggunaan multimedia lainnya seperti TV atau film dalam meningkatkan kemampuan listening mahasiswa.

Kata kunci: Lagu, Listening Comprehension, Universitas

The demand for English language proficiency among students is rising. More specifically, listening comprehension has recently attracted considerable attention in university student. Despite students having mastered the basic elements of English such as grammar and vocabulary, their listening comprehension is in general weak. Listening skill is one of the four skills that the students learn in their classroom. Listening also plays the main aspect of receptive skill in English learning, as stated by Feyten (1991) listening has emerged as an important component in the process of second language acquisition. Listening provides the aural input that serves as the basis for language acquisition and enables learners to interact in spoken communication.

Listening is the first language mode that children acquire. It provides the foundation for all aspects of language and cognitive development, and it plays a life-long role in the processes of communication. Wilt (1990) reported that people listen 45 percent of the time they spend communicating. This study is still widely cited (e.g., Martin, 1987; Strother, 1987. Wilt found that 30 percent of communication time was spent speaking, 16 percent reading, and 9 percent writing. That finding confirmed what Rankin discovered in 1928, that people spent 70 percent of their waking time communicating and those

three-fourths of this time was spent listening and speaking.

One of the techniques that the lecture can use is using song in teaching listening. Using song will make the student interest in joining listening class. The students feel bored when the listening class always proposes the same kind of audio, in this study the lecture implemented songs because doing so was an interesting resource used by English lectures. In fact, they have used songs as a resource to develop communicative abilities properly in a foreign language, providing students with the opportunity to talk with confidence and giving teachers the chance to teach in a fun way.

According to Lo and Li (1998), songs are able to change the monotonous mood in the class and with the smoothing effect of music; they provide a comfortable class environment so that students can develop their lingual skills more easily. Besides, utilizing songs in class environment amuses students, helps them feel relaxed and get rid of their negative attitudes towards a foreign language while learning a lingual structure through a song (Saricoban, 2000).

Songs offer many codes that strengthen student memory such as choruses, rhymes and melodies (Maley, 1987). Therefore, these codes in songs increase the functionality of songs in

language teaching. When a student listens to and memorizes a song involved in the class, the lyrics are embedded in his/her long-term memory. Moreover, neurological researches have shown that musical and lingual processes occur in the same section of brain and that there are significant similarities between musical and lingual syntax (Maess, Koelsch, Gunter, & Friederici, 2001). According to Cheung (2001), as students more easily learn the things about which they have background knowledge, student motivation is increased when the elements belonging to the popular culture of the target language are involved in the class. Bringing a song listened by the student to the class environment increases students' desire to learn and enables them contribute to the process of learning by making use of their own musical knowledge.

The paper aims at identifying the reasons that using song in teaching listening comprehension in university. In addition, the paper's goal is to highlight the main obstacles facing by the students in acquiring listening skills. The paper also analyzes the song technique used to master the listening skills. More specifically, the paper will try to answer the following questions: 1. What are the impacts of using song-learning English? 2. How frequently listening song used to improve the listening skills for student? 3. What are the common difficulties that face the respondents in the

questionnaire implemented in this paper in terms of listening comprehension?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Listening Comprehension

Howatt and Dakin (1974) stated that listening is the ability to identify and understand what others are saying. This process involves understanding a speaker's accent or pronunciation, the speaker's grammar and vocabulary, and comprehension of meaning. An able listener is capable of doing these four things simultaneously. In terms of language processing, it is now generally accepted that learners need access to both top-down as well as bottom-up processing strategies. Bottom-up processing strategies focus on the individual components of spoken and written messages, i.e. phonemes, graphemes, individual words and grammatical elements which need to be comprehended in order to understand messages. Top-down processing strategies, on the other hand, focus on macro-features of text such as the writer or speaker's purpose, topic of the message, the overall structure of the text (Nunan, 1991, p. 4).

Bottom-up listening involves the listener in scanning the input to identify familiar lexical items, segmenting the stream of speech into constituents, for example, in order to recognize that (a book of mine) consists of four words. In addition,

bottom-up listening helps the listener in using phonological cues to identify the information in an utterance format. Finally, bottom-up listening helps the listener use grammatical cues to organize the inputs into constituents, for example, in order to recognize that in the book which I lent you (the book) and (which I lent you) are major constituents rather than (the book which I) and (lent you). Top-down listening strategies, on the other hand, involve the listener in assigning an interaction to part of a particular event, such as storytelling, joking, praying, complaining, assigning persons, places, and things to categories, inferring cause and effect relationships, anticipating outcomes, inferring the topic of a discourse, inferring the sequence between events, and inferring missing details (Richards, 1990)

In the context of English Academic Purposes (EAP), the listening skills required in a strictly academic sense are those needed for listening to lectures. However, the use of media is also of potential academic interest as news broadcasting and documentaries are all potentially valuable learning aids (McErlain & Ramón Carande, 1999). Listening is often erroneously considered a passive skill. In fact, in order to decode a message that the speaker is delivering, the listener must actively contribute knowledge from both linguistic and non-linguistic sources. The view of listening would

involve the learner in listening to the message without paying attention to its component elements.

Listening to a language can be defined as the ability to receive and decode oral communication by processing a language sample (McErlain & Ramón Carande, 1999). Ronald and Roskelly (1986) define listening as an active process requiring the same skills of prediction, hypothesizing, checking, revising, and generalizing that writing and reading demand; and these authors present specific exercises to make students active listeners who are aware of the "inner voice" one hears when writing. In other words, listening is a two-way process involving reception, decoding of input, and production that involves predicting and compensating.

The Influence of Songs in Foreign Language Classes

According to Lo and Li (1998), songs are able to change the monotonous mood in the class and with the soothing effect of music; they provide a comfortable class environment so that students can develop their lingual skills more easily. Besides, utilizing songs in class environment amuses students, helps them feel relaxed and get rid of their negative attitudes towards a foreign language while learning a lingual structure through a song (Saricoban, 2000). In this direction, the amusing and relaxing mood brought by songs to the class eases the

effects of certain emotional cases such as excitement, anxiety, lack of self-confidence and the feeling of being threatened, in addition to influencing learning process positively or facilitating it by stimulating the student emotionally (Kramersch, 1993).

Songs also help motivating the learners as they provide a pleasant atmosphere. The students are encouraged to actively involve in the learning process by making use of their musical knowledge. In this way songs help students to develop confidence for language learning (Şahin, 2008). According to Orlova (2003) these are some of the advantages for working in class with songs:

- Practicing the rhythm, stress and the intonation patterns of the English language.
- Teaching vocabulary, especially in the vocabulary reinforcement stage.
- Teaching grammar. In this respect, teachers while investigating the use of the tenses especially favor songs.
- Teaching speaking. For this purpose, songs and mainly their lyrics are employed as a stimulus for class discussions.
- Teaching listening. Music can be helpful for comprehension.
- Developing writing skills. For this purpose a song can be used in a variety of ways; for example, speculation as to what could happen to the characters in

the future, writing a letter to the main character, etc.

The Criteria for Selecting Songs in Language Teaching

Songs are essential sources to be utilized during language teaching. Besides positive effects, there are of course difficulties encountered while using songs in language teaching. Terhune (1997: 8) lines these difficulties as follows:

1. Pop songs are not scientific. Therefore, some teachers and students do not think that they are effective tools in education.
2. As each student has a different way of learning, some students may have difficulty in studying through music.
3. Inefficient sound systems in schools may cause problems while listening to songs.
4. The types of music favored by students may not be matching with each other.
5. Songs that are not grammatical or those involving complicated sentence structures may confuse students.
6. In some songs, there may be embarrassing parts that cannot be explained to students.
7. Repetition of a limited number of words may cause the song to seem boring or ineffective.

According to Jensen (2000), many teachers do not have sufficient knowledge about music and teacher-training programs

do not involve anything regarding how to utilize music in language teaching. Another disadvantage of using songs is the lack of the ability to slow down the tempo of the song when a grammatically difficult part is playing, or to fasten it when there is the repetition of certain parts (Miller, 2002). Moreover, some teachers may think that they cannot sing, but using songs in the classroom for this aim does not necessitate any expertise in this field. Teachers can accompany the song while it is playing or in cases where students do not prefer to sing a song alone.

While utilizing a song in classroom environment, the language of that song, age and language level of the students, areas in which students and the teacher are interested in should be taken into account. In order to utilize songs in the best way, a certain amount of attention is required. Sariçoban (2000) recommends using songs that harbor frequent repetitions or a story or interpretations on life or cultural elements. Griffe (1992) lists four elements to be considered while choosing a song to be used in the class as follows:

1. Classroom environment (number, age and interests of students; lesson hours)
2. Teacher (teacher's age, interest in music and aim to use the song in the class)
3. Classroom facilities (flexibility in lesson plan, classroom equipment)

4. Music (lesson plan and equipment such as the volume, sources of music, copying machine, board, etc.)

Some songs may contain embarrassing elements for students. Sariçoban (2000) divides songs into two categories as those suitable for adults on advanced level of language and those appropriate for children. Meaningful and popular songs which also harbor cultural elements as well as grammatical patterns should be chosen for adult students on intermediate or advanced level, whereas more familiar or internationally-known songs should be selected for children. Griffe (1992) recommends using short and slow songs for students on beginner level. Crosswords, drawing or picture showing exercises can be conducted with such songs. For the students with a higher language level, long and fast songs that tell a story should be used. The song to be chosen should have a clear sound and it should be comprehensible; there should not be too many instruments played with a high volume in the song.

Activities that can be Applied through the Utilization of Songs

Activities that can be carried out with songs in foreign language classes can be classified in three groups as pre-listening, listening and post-listening activities. Here, a teacher should carefully think about what a student will do before, while and after listening. Below are some

recommendations regarding these activity stages and what kind of activities a teacher can use in these stages.

Pre-listening activities

In this stage, the teacher ensures that students are ready for the listening activity to be carried out. According to Davenellos (1999), the aim of this stage is to prepare students to a topic grammatically, educationally and psychologically. Before playing a song to students, it is necessary to introduce the topic, the keywords and the grammatical structure. In this stage, in order to activate students' background information, it may be suitable to ask the students to guess the theme of a song, to brainstorm about it, to present or to discuss the cultural information that the song includes or to state the keywords and the ideas in the song. Pre-listening activities enable students to be aware of the purpose of listening to the song and to focus on the meaning of the song while listening. Besides, it is also possible to use songs by deliberately removing a part of their lyrics and to conduct activities in which students predict or derive the meaning of a word out of the context (Vandergrift, 1999). As pre-listening activities, Sariçoban (2000) recommends discussing the theme, the title or the story of the song if there is one, informing students about the lingual points to be studied and using a picture to introduce the theme of the song.

Listening Activities

Listening activities are directly related to the text and students are expected to carry out these activities in the course of listening. In this process of listening and by the guidance of the teacher, students control their comprehension skills and focus on listening to the text. According to Peachey (2003), in order for students to get accustomed to the voice of the singer or the tempo of the song, they need to listen to that song at least for three or four times. Prior to listening, it is also necessary to grant students with a short period of time for reading the questions they are going to answer while listening.

In this stage, activities such as removing certain parts of the text which are related with the grammatical form, word or pronunciation type in question, checking the accuracy of the predictions made about the song before listening, ordering the lyrics of the song, answering multiple-choice or open-ended questions about the song, picking the words that students hear in the song from a long wordlist given before listening, pausing the song and asking students to repeat the last word they have heard or correcting lexical, grammatical or syntactical mistakes deliberately involved in the lyrics.

Post-listening activities

Various activities for assessing the whole process of listening can be conducted

in this stage. According to Davenellos (1999), this stage consists of follow-up activities for developing speaking and writing skills.

In this stage, Sariçoban (2000) recommends using activities such as reading a text about the singer or the theme of the song, commenting and interpreting the song and dramatizing the plot of the song. These activities may vary in accordance with the language level and the areas of interest of students. The teacher can check the answers of the questions from listening stage. For improving writing skills, students can compose a dialogue out of the words of the people in a song; they can summarize, continue the song, or rewrite the lyrics from the point of view of another person in the song. In order to improve pronunciation, students can sing the song individually, with another student or in groups. For improving speaking skills, students can talk about how they feel after listening to the song. Also, some questions can be directed to students with the aim of initiating discussions.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used descriptive qualitative method. The subjects of the study were students at sixth semester of Muhammadiyah University of Jakarta. The instrument and the procedure of data collection were used observation and questionnaire. The activities of the

implementation involved the use of song in teaching listening. In this paper, the author approaches listening skills from the perspective of students in classroom. A questionnaire is used as a neutral tool so as to find out the kind of methods used in teaching English skills and the kind of difficulties students face.

For purpose of the paper, the author distributed the questionnaire among to take the data from 6th semester of English department in Muhammadiyah University of Jakarta. Participants in the questionnaire were homogenous in terms of linguistic skills, socioeconomic background, educational system, and field of study. The concept of this paper was given to students in the classroom through their lectures. The author intentionally avoided conducting personal interviews with the students to give those participants the freedom to answer the questions and express themselves without any interference by the author

DISCUSSION AND DATA ANALYSIS

Based on the questioner result shows, it becomes clear that out of the total number of students 90% like or have an interest in learning English language skill. On the other hand, those students do not have interest in learning English language skills amount 10%. It is to be noticed that there is no big gap between those who expressed interest in

learning English and those who did not show the same interest.

The factors that affect students' interest in learning can be shown as the table 1 below.

Table 1
Percentage of factors that affect students' interest in learning

Factors	Percentage	Total of Respondent
Real Life	40%	100
Fun to do	40%	100
Prestige	20%	100

Based on the table it can be conclude several things as follows:

1. Importance of English in real life. The percentage is 40%.
2. Desire to learn foreign language because it is fun thing to do. The percentage is 40%
3. Prestige in social life. The percentage is 20%

Total percentage of the student with no interest in learning English can be describe as in table 2.

Table 2
Percentage of students with no interesting learning English

Method of Learning	Percentage	Total respondent
Using radio	4.5%	100
Without radio	95.5%	100

The students who expressed no interest in learning English, the total percentage are 25%. The author believes that this number is still low. Some of the reasons mentioned by these students for not being interested in learning English include: hardship they face in learning English; no enough time to learn; lack of continuity for learning English and learning English not to use it in communication.

The importance of utilizing learning tools, which is the topic of this paper, in mastering English language skills cannot be underestimated. Table 2 clearly indicates that using radio, as a learning tool is low when compared with other tools or methods. More specifically, the percentage of respondents who used radio was 4.5% while 95.5% of the students do not use radio. It is expected that the rationale for the former students not to use the radio as a learning method can be contributed to their weakness in listening comprehension.

Using TV and tape recorder also plays important rules to learn English as mention in the table below:

Table 3
The percentage of students' learning listening method

Method of Learning	Percentage	Total respondent
Using TV	30%	100
Tape recorder method	70%	100

TV occupies the first place among other learning methods. Around 70% of the total students use TV. The reason for this overwhelming use of TV can be contributed to the joy and entertainment one experience when watching TV so that students attention are attracted to the images displayed on TV. According to the data found, dependence on tape recorder to learn English language skills is low. As a matter of fact, just 30%, said that they use this method to learn English. To put in a different way, 70% students said that they do not use the tape recorder method. The author believes that these statistics are disappointing as the percentage of those using tape recorder should be higher since this method is easy to use, has low cost to own, and it can be easy moved from one place to another. Moreover, using the tape recorder can help students record their own statements and hear again. It is unfortunate that the methods of radio and tape recorder are not well used although they have so many benefits in helping students improve their listening comprehension.

The presence of a lecture in a classroom is considered among the most important tools used in learning English language skills including listening comprehension. However, according the study conducted for the purpose of this article, it becomes clear to the author that lecture rarely use radio or TV as learning

method. Somewhat, teachers use some audio. It is clear that there is weakness and limitation in using the different kinds of learning methods although some of these methods are easy to use and cheap to own. Therefore, using different learning methods should be inseparable part of the teacher's way of teaching English skills.

Analyzing the data collected for this paper points out that 70% of respondents have improved their listening comprehension via the lecture while the remaining percentage have not learnt much. In addition, students' listening comprehension based on the use of radio, TV, and tape recorder was very good (60%), good (25%), and weak (15%) respectively. As to the degree of satisfaction among students for the method used to learn listening comprehension skills for English language, about 50% of students were satisfied, 40% were moderately satisfied, and 10% less or minimally satisfied. it is also can be noted that:

1. Speech speed by the speaker affect 80% of students in their ability to master listening comprehension of the English language while the other 20% of students do not consider speech speed an obstacle in the face of learning. The author believes that it is in the best interest of the first group of student to continue listening of the English language through the use of

assisting tools to develop their listening skills.

2. Limited knowledge of vocabulary and structure of sentences constitute a hardship for 70% while 30% consider (limited) knowledge of vocabulary and structure of sentences do not amount to an obstacle in the face of developing their listening skills in English.
3. One of the reasons that students face a hard time in listening comprehension is limited knowledge of the topic in question. About 75% face difficulties in following up in discussion because they do not know fully the subject matter of discussion. On the other hand, 25% stated that their listening comprehension skill is not affected by their limited knowledge of the topic.

Based on the interviewed of the participants, 80% of them believe that the use of song in listening class improve their understanding about new vocabularies, new kind of sentences and expand their knowledge about the western song and the way that the singer pronounce the words. 20% of participant felt confuse in understanding new words and getting the meaning of the lyric. So, 20% participants need an extra explanation in catching the meaning of the song. The implementation of song strategy gives students a joyful impression in listening class, especially in handling the unknown words found in lyric.

Using the song strategy enhances not only students' vocabulary interpretation ability, but also their involvement in teaching and learning process as well as their motivation in listening class. Concerning the use of song strategy, it does help the students to be more confident and independent in dealing with English learning. It facilitates the students not too depend and rely too much on their lecture in finding the suitable song to learn English. It can be seen that the students were eager to find the other song that they can use to increase their listening skill. This strategy encouraged students to point out their ideas, thought and initiative that they actually could infer the meaning of the unknown words they found in lyric without simply opened their dictionary or consulted to their lecture.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The use of technology needs to be exploited in classroom as much as possible. For this reason, utilizing technology for language teaching is of great importance, and the tendency to integrate technology with lesson content grows each day. Accordingly, utilizing songs through technology in lesson environment attract attention. There are positive and negative views on the utilization of songs in foreign language teaching. It is seen that songs are

used for many reasons by methods adopted in foreign language teaching. The facts that music soothes students and that melodies, rhythms and rhymes in a song facilitate language learning improve students' reading, writing, speaking and listening skills.

Music and songs are all authentic texts. These authentic texts act as significant sources for students to discover the culture of the target language and to improve their cultural awareness. In this study, which was carried out by taking these effects of songs as basis, activities that can be used with songs in Turkish as a foreign language classes are given and certain sample activities are recommended. For foreign language teaching, if songs are carefully chosen by taking the audience objectives, language level of students and song content into consideration and if deliberate activities are carried out, it is possible to make use of songs effectively.

Utilizing songs this way provides an enjoyable experience not only for students but also for the lecture. Using songs along with such activities will have many advantages such as saving the lesson from being boring and monotonous and improving student motivation. Finally, we should bear in mind that every day our profession is more demanding and we have to be ready to face the challenges that come up, finding solutions or different alternatives

to overcome limitations. Therefore, we should admit that the intention to do a project like this is to look for better strategies with which to teach, going beyond the results, and that this search comprises a non-stop activity that we as a lecture have to keep in mind.

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